

Semi-transparent blade-coated FAPbBr₃ perovskite solar cells: A scalable low-temperature manufacturing process under ambient condition

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Abstract

Perovskite photovoltaics is an emerging PV technology that attracts interest thanks to an unprecedented combination of properties, including the ease of the bandgap tunability. The feasibility to deploy wide bandgap absorbers (>2.2 eV) leading to high average visible transmittance (AVT) is particularly intriguing for building-integrated photovoltaics, in particular for smart windows, façades and agrivoltaics. However, research on this topic is still at the initial stage, especially concerning the development of scalable deposition techniques. Uniform coverage and morphology control of bromide perovskite film are the main issue to tackle. In this work, a systematic study on the development of FAPbBr₃-based semi-transparent PSC is presented by replacing spin-coating as main deposition technique used for the device fabrication. To tackle this topic, blade coating technique is employed to obtain a manufacturing flow performed at low temperature in air environment. The results for blade coated device shows PCE of 5.8 %, AVT of 52.3 % and bifacial factor of 86.5 %.

Moreover, scalable and uniform FAPbBr₃ deposition on 300cm² substrates is presented for the first time. The combination of low temperature, scale-up capability and air processing along with promising photovoltaic performances represent a feasible platform for future exploitation of PSC in BIPV.

Introduction

Semi-transparent (ST) solar cells have attracted attention due to their promising applications in building integrated photovoltaic (BIPV) ^[1, 2], tandem devices ^[3] and wearable electronics [5]. The important metrics for transparent photovoltaics (TPV) are the power conversion efficiency (PCE), the average visible transmittance (AVT) and the color rendering index (CRI). In order to compare the performance of TPV technologies, Light Utilization Efficiency (LUE) has been introduced by Traverse et al. in 2017 ^[2]. In BIPV, Si-based PV technologies are still dominating the market by addressing the demand of visible transparency with the use of spatially segmented opaque c-Si cells without achieving the aesthetical and transparency requirements of a building façade^[2]. Emergent third-generation PV technologies such as Dye Sensitized ^[4], Organic ^[5] and Perovskite ^[6, 7] can be potential candidates in BIPV field. Perovskite solar cells (PSC) appears as the ideal choice in this respect, owing to the easy tunable bandgap. In fact, by alloying chloride, bromide and iodide the bandgap of lead perovskites can be continuously tuned from 1.4 eV to above 3 eV ^[7, 8]. This property has been mostly investigated in high efficiency Si-HJT/PSC tandem solar cells, implementing a perovskite film with suitable bandgap (1.65-1.70 eV) overcoming 30 % PCE ^[9]. The interest on perovskites with a bandgap wider than 2 eV have been directed mostly to applications alternative to photovoltaics, such as light emitting devices and photodetectors^[10, 11]. Nonetheless, power conversion efficiencies above 10 % have been demonstrated by optimizing bromide perovskites (APbBr₃) in opaque device stack ^[12]. Bromide perovskites have a bandgap around 2.3 eV, with a Shockley-Quiesser efficiency limit around 15 % but with high ceiling for visible transparency ^[13]. Additionally, bromide perovskites comprising a single A-site cations such as methylammonium (MA),

formamidinium (FA) and cesium, are highly stable in the photoactive phase, differently from iodide perovskites ^[14]. Here we selected FAPbBr₃ as perovskite absorber aiming at the higher thermal stability of FA-based perovskites when compared to MA-based ones ^[15]. Indeed, MAPbX₃ decomposes to gaseous methylamine and hydrogen iodide when exposed to heat and moisture, resulting in loss of optical absorption and severe electron-hole recombination ^[16]. On the other hand, the synthesis of FAPbBr₃ is expected to be easier than CsPbBr₃, for which high temperature are usually required and the control over the phase purity is challenging ^[17]. Additionally, Zhumekenov et al. reported long carrier diffusion lengths of 19 μm for FaPbBr₃ crystals ^[18], which is among the largest reported values in halide perovskite materials.

The FAPbBr₃ perovskite having a band gap of 2.23 eV, reached a maximum 10% of PCE in opaque devices using SnO₂/FAPbBr₃/SpiroOmetad/Gold structure deposited by spin coating deposition ^[19]. Grancini et al. studied the beneficial introduction of Cs⁺ cation in FAPbBr₃ deposited by spin coating deposition ^[20] while Ying et al. focused on moving the FAPbBr₃ deposition from spin to blade coating with the aim of scaling up the deposition area (>1 cm²) ^[21]. Best results showed a PCE of 7.29 % using opaque high-temperature processed FTO\TiO₂\FAPbBr₃\Spiro-OMeTAD\Au device stack. By replacing the gold with silver nanowires, the PCE decreased to 5.25 % showing Average Visible Transmittance (AVT) of 25 % and Light Utilization Efficiency (LUE) of 1.31 %. FAPbBr₃ has been also used for PIN devices deposited by spin coating deposition reaching a maximum PCE of 5.71%, AVT of 35 % and LUE of 1.99 ^[22]. The blade coating method is successfully known for its numerous advantages in comparison to spin coating ^[23]. Indeed, while spin coating is a well-established deposition method for small-area cells, solvent evaporation and the kinetics of crystallization growth during the deposition become critical as the active area increases ^[24]. On the other hand, the control of morphology/quality of the film is quite challenging if compared to spin coating ^[23, 24].

In this work, we present a systematic study on the fabrication process of highly transparent devices based on ITO/SnO₂/FaPbBr₃/PTAA/ITO device stack. We selected SnO₂ and PTAA as electron

transport layer (ETL) and hole transport layer (HTL), respectively, to limit the processing temperature below than 100°C, permitting to extend the fabrication procedure discussed in this work to flexible plastic substrates ^[25]. The SnO₂ has been deemed as ideal ETL due to high carrier mobility, low parasitic absorbance in the visible spectrum, high chemical stability and insensitivity to ultraviolet (UV) light ^[26]. The PTAA polymer has been tested in both NIP and PIN device architecture showing great potential in terms of PV performance ^[27], long-term stability ^[28] and tolerance to the sputtering damage ^[29]. We consider several fabrication processes from fully spin-coated (SC) to fully blade-coated (BC) devices. For spin-coated samples, we obtained a maximum PCE of 8.11 % and AVT of 47.4 % corresponding to a LUE equal to 3.8 that represent one of the higher PCE in literature for FAPbBr₃ based device made at low temperature processing. For fully blade-coated devices, we replaced SC technique with BC for all the constituent layers forming the stack (SnO₂, FAPbBr₃ and PTAA) reaching PCE equal to 5.8 %, AVT of 52.3 % and LUE equal to 3. Moreover, the fully blade-coated device demonstrated a bifaciality factor of 86.5 % (defined as $PCE_{\text{rear}}/PCE_{\text{front}}$), a remarkably high value if compared to those shown in literature ^[30, 31]. Bifacial solar cells are able to collect photons from incident and albedo radiation reaching both the front side and rear side of a solar module, which is highly interesting for Agrivoltaics field ^[32]. Finally, we demonstrated the uniformity and the PL stability of the FAPbBr₃ at 100 cm²-sized substrate by performing spatial PL maps for future application on perovskite solar module.

Results and Discussion

Semitransparent PSCs (ST-PSCs) have been fabricated using a planar N-I-P architecture consisting in the following stack: ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃/PTAA/ITO. The entire fabrication process is performed at low-temperature (<100°C). The final goal of this work is to demonstrate a fully blade-coated (BC) device by gradually replacing the spin coating technique for the deposition of the constituent layers. In **Figure 1**, we show the sample types investigated in this work, hereafter named Sample A, Sample

B, Sample C and Sample D. Sample A and B are fabricated using spin-coated FAPbBr₃ perovskite by replacing the SC (Sample A) with BC (Sample B) for SnO₂ layer. On the contrary, Sample C and D are based on blade-coated FAPbBr₃ perovskite by replacing the SC (Sample C) with BC (Sample D) for PTAA layer. Sample A and D represents Fully SC and BC devices, respectively. The icons clarified the deposition technique used for the deposition of each layer (SnO₂, FAPbBr₃ and PTAA) of each sample type.

Figure 1. Device structures optimized in this work based on Glass-ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃/PTAA/ITO: Replacement of spin coating with blade coating of each layer forming the device stack.

In **Figure 2**, we report the results about the investigation on structural and morphological properties of the FAPbBr₃ perovskite deposited by varying the deposition technique and method (Sample A vs. Sample D) are reported in **Figure 2**. X-Ray diffraction (XRD in **Figure 2a**), shows peaks attributed to ITO accordingly to JCPDS card number 32-0458 are highlighted. FAPbBr₃ reflections are labeled accordingly to literature and the patterns perfectly match perovskite pure α -phase for both samples [10, 33]. Despite having similar quality in term of crystallinity, it is noticeable that h00 orientation is relatively more privileged in the blade coated film. In fact, the ratio of the integrated intensities

between the peaks (100), (200) and (300) to those indexed as (210) and (211) is significantly higher for the blade coated sample. The possibility to manipulate the texture of the perovskite thin film by modifying the deposition method (spin coating vs blade coating) and the crystallization technique (solvent quenching method vs. sequential deposition), also reported in literature,^[34] is an interesting finding aiming at future investigation and exploitation of the (eventual) anisotropy of FAPbBr₃ perovskite thin films optoelectronic properties.

Notably, blade-coated perovskite has been obtained starting from CsBr-doped PbBr₂ that helps to solubilize the PbBr₂ in DMSO avoiding the formation of needle-like crystal after storage (**Figure S2**). We speculate that the small amount of CsBr-doping (less than 3% in molar ratio) is not contributing to structural changes on the final FAPbBr₃ perovskite as confirmed by XRD diffractograms in **Figure 2a**.

AFM images (**Figure 2b-c** and **Figure S3**) at 10x10 μm² were collected upon different surface portions for each sample and a statistical (**Figure 2d**) analysis was performed to observe the surface roughness evolution as a function of the different deposition methods. The surface roughness of the spin-coated and blade-coated FAPbBr₃ perovskites are markedly different where the spin coated perovskite displays a lower RMS roughness (20-30 nm) with respect to the blade coated perovskite (40-50 nm) for all the AFM scan areas (100, 400, 900 μm²).

Planar SEM images (Figure 2e and 2f) show the morphology of the perovskite layers in good agreement with those reported in AFM measurements. We can notice, for both deposition methods, the presence of μm-scale size grains interconnected each other with smaller sub-micrometer size grains. However, spin-coated perovskite does not present pin-holes at the grain boundaries if compared with blade-coated perovskite as expected from the lower surface roughness. This aspect becomes even more relevant if considered the successive deposition of PTAA polymer with extremely low film thickness of around 30nm.

Figure 2. (a) XRD patterns of spin-coated (red line) and blade-coated (black line) FAPbBr₃ on ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃ samples. Each diffraction peak is associated to the crystalline layers (perovskite and ITO). (b-c) AFM images of the FAPbBr₃ films with AFM scan Area of 100 μm², collected for the spin-coated (b) and blade-coated FAPbBr₃ films–(c). d) Root mean square (RMS) roughness measured by AFM images with different scan areas (100, 400, 900 μm²) for spin-coated and blade-coated films. e-f) Planar SEM images of the FAPbBr₃ films deposited by SC (e) and BC (f). The scale bar is 2μm for both SEM images.

The first step towards a fully blade-coated device stack is the deposition of the SnO₂ as ETL. For the optimization of the blade-coated SnO₂ layer (Sample B), we fabricated 0.4cm²-sized ST-PSC by varying the dilution of the SnO₂ nanoparticle (np-SnO₂) dispersion in deionized (DI) water. For the spin-coated devices (Sample A), we fixed the dilution (1:5 volume ratio) in DI water of the np-SnO₂ ink [35]. For Sample B, we evaluated three different dilutions (1:5, 1:3, No dilution) fabricating batches of 32 devices for each. In figure 3, we report the statistical dispersion of the PCE results using the three different dilution of the np-SnO₂ inks. The results show the presence of not negligible number of cells (hereafter called “dead cells”) with low PCE (< 2%), mainly ascribed to shunting issue (low V_{oc}). The number of “dead cells” remarkably decreased at low dilutions (1:3 and No dilution) of the np-SnO₂ ink being equal to 18, 10, 8. This is mainly related to the enhanced coverage of the SnO₂ layer at low dilution avoiding shunting paths at SnO₂/FAPbBr₃ interface^[36]. It is important to note

that 1:5 dilution experienced lack of reproducible results for both spin-coated (Sample A) and blade-coated (Sample B) showing 50% and 56 % of dead cells in the batch, respectively.

For working cells, the PCE results are reported as a normal distribution ranging from 2 % to 8 % showing the following average values for the three tested dilutions: 24 for No dilution, 23 for 1:3 and 14 for 1:5. With aim of improve the reproducibility of the results, we found the best compromise between reproducibility and PCE results using 1:3 dilution, leading to an average PCE of 4.65%. In **Figure S4**, the optimized blade-coated SnO₂ layer was further characterized by AFM to evaluate the morphology, the surface coverage and the roughness of the layer. The results show extremely homogeneous and smooth surface with roughness of around 1nm acquired at different surface areas.

Figure 3. Normal distribution of the PCE results obtained on a batch of 32 ST-PSC devices for each dilution of the SnO₂ nanoparticle ink: No dilution, 1:3 SnO₂: water; 1:5 SnO₂: water

In **Figure 4a**, we report the statistical distribution of PCE results obtained for the different samples (A, B, C and D) introduced in **Figure 1**. The J-V characteristics and maximum power point tracking

(MPPT) for tested cells are also reported in **Figure S5**. The average PV parameters (V_{oc} , J_{sc} , FF, PCE) are reported in **Tab S1**. PCE results do not change significantly comparing the SnO_2 layers deposited by SC (Sample A) and BC (Sample B) with average PCE of 7.1% and 6.7%, respectively, thanks to the optimization of the SnO_2 nanoparticle ink. The PCE comparison of ST-PSC based on the perovskite layer made by SC and BC (highlighted in **Figure 4a**), Sample B and Sample C, respectively, show a remarkable decrease of the PCE mainly attributed to decrease in J_{sc} showing 7.9 and 6.4 mA/cm^2 , respectively. The discrepancy in J_{sc} is mainly due to the lower FAPbBr_3 perovskite thickness obtained for blade-coated Sample C with respect to spin-coated sample B being equal to 200nm and 350nm, respectively (see **Figure S6**). This is also evident by comparing the IPCE spectra of the two cells as reported in **Figure 4b** where the IPCE decrease in the range of wavelengths from 380nm to 530nm is related to the lower light absorption of the Sample C. On the opposite, the BC of PTAA (Sample D) introduces only a small reduction of PCE and IPCE. The BC deposition of thicker FAPbBr_3 layers (~400nm) is challenging due to the lack of control on the perovskite crystallization and growth. In **Figure S7**, we reported the planar SEM images of the FAPbBr_3 obtained by increasing the film thickness. The presence of perovskite cuboids at the film surface leads to haze and rougher films. The analysis of the UV-Visible transmittance allows us to link the lower current generation to the lower light harvesting from blade-coated perovskites. In fact, the transmittance of spin-coated perovskites attains a low value below 10 % at the band edge (around 540nm) while the one from blade coated perovskites is remains around 20 %. The difference of 15 % in transmittance in the range between 400 nm and 550 nm closely fit the one in IPCE. Notably, the lower light absorption enhances the AVT of blade-coated devices up to 52 %, above the 47 % from spin-coated devices as shown in **Figure 4c**. In order to compare the SC and BC deposition at the same thickness, we lowered the thickness of the spin-coated FAPbBr_3 perovskite by reducing the SC solution concentration from 1.4M to 1.1M. The J-V results shows the following PV parameters: $V_{oc} = 1.44 \text{ V}$, $J_{sc} = 6.94 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$, $\text{FF} = 64.7 \%$, $\text{PCE} = 6.5 \%$. Finally, the BC of the PTAA polymer were optimized in Sample D by varying the coating speed from 5 mm/s to 100 mm/s in order to replace the layer by SC. In **Figure S8**,

the transmittance spectra of the ITO/PTAA samples deposited by varying the BC speed and compared with spin-coated PTAA sample deposited at the same concentration. From the results, 100 mm/s was chosen as BC speed for device fabrication.

The metrics for TPV devices (J-V parameters, AVT and LUE) for champion devices are reported in **Tab.1**. Notably, the LUE parameter was greater than 3% in fully blade-coated device (Sample D) showing the good potential of the developed process for ST-PSCs if compared to the other transparent PV technologies [2].

Figure 4. a) Statistical PCE results obtained on a batch of six devices for each device stack structure by measuring at 1 Sun AM1.5G illumination condition under reverse and forward scan directions. b) IPCE spectra and integrated currents of the ST-PSC devices following the device stack shown in Figure 1. c) Representative transmittance spectra obtained for Sample A (fully spin-coated) and Sample D (fully blade-coated) device stacks, d) IPCE and 100-R spectra measured by illuminating

form the front (solid lines) and rear side (dashed lines) in Sample D. e) Normalized PV parameters measured during dry heat test at 85°C in air by following ISOS-D2 stability protocol.

Table 1. PV parameters of champion ST-PSC cells for each structure

Sample	Scan	Voc (V)	FF (%)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	Integrated Jsc (mA/cm ²)	PCE (%)	AVT (%)	LUE (%)
Sample A	Reverse	1.44	67.0	-8.3	-8.4	8.0	47	3.8
	Forward	1.43	73.6	-7.7		8.1		
Sample B	Reverse	1.45	61.1	-8.2	-8.0	7.3		
	Forward	1.44	53.8	-8.3		6.5		
Sample C	Reverse	1.43	68.3	-6.1	-7.0	6.0		
	Forward	1.42	51.3	-6.5		4.7		
Sample D	Reverse	1.41	58.0	-7.0	-6.8	5.8	52	3.0
	Forward	1.40	52.1	-6.5		4.8		

An important feature of semi-transparent PV field is the bifacial illumination: a strategy to increase the output of the PV system working with the reflected light from the ground. In Sample D, we measured the PV performance illuminating the device from the front (glass-SnO₂-Perovskite-PTAA-ITO) and rear side (ITO-PTAA-Perovskite-SnO₂-glass) reaching 5.1 % and 4.4%, respectively (**Table S2**). A remarkable high bifaciality factor of 86.5 % was obtained if compared with results reported in literature ^[31, 37]. In **Figure 4d**, we reported the IPCE spectra by varying the illumination side in Sample D device. The results showed lower IPCE and integrated current density in rear side illumination due to the reflection of the sputtered ITO electrode and the parasitic absorbance of the PTAA layer. A higher reflectance illuminating from air/sputtered-ITO interface is measured in comparison with air/glass/commercial-ITO (front) interface. To demonstrate this, we plot the 100-R spectra by varying the illumination side showing higher reflectance in the entire range of wavelengths corresponding to current losses of about 0.3 mA/cm². Moreover, the parasitic absorption of the PTAA contributed to current losses of about 0.4mA/cm². In Figure 4e, we reported the results of dry heat stability test performed on Sample D device following the ISOS-D2 protocol for 1000h ^[38]. The not-

encapsulated ST-PSC cell was stored in an oven at 85°C in air and measured during the ageing time (200h, 400h, 600h, 800h, 1000h). Interestingly, the device retained 95% of the initial PCE value without suffering any degradation. This is due to the presence of sputtered ITO top contact that efficiently works also as encapsulating material preserving the cell from moisture-driven degradation.

In order to exploit the spatial uniformity of blade-coated stack, we prepared ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃ and ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃/PTAA stacks on 12x10cm² (**Figure 5a**) sized substrates, then cut to 10x10cm² (**Figure 5b**) to perform PL analysis. The FAPbBr₃ deposition was performed by employing a dipping process in the second step of the sequential deposition that might influence the thin film uniformity. We characterized the 10x10cm² samples by employing a hyperspectral photoluminescence imaging system. Such technique allows to acquire three dimensional datasets {x,y,λ}, with two dimensions being spatial and the third one representing PL intensity (I_{PL}) as a function of the wavelength. Therefore, each pixel of the measured image contains I_{PL} vs wavelength (λ) information. Importantly, this method is contactless, hence it can be used at any step of device fabrication, allowing to probe the optoelectronic properties not only of full devices but also of half stacks or bare absorbers^[39]. Here, we observe a good coverage over the whole surface of the sample for both half stack (ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃) and full stack (ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃/PTAA), as shown in the PL maximal intensity (I_{PLmax}) maps reported in **Figure 5c** and **Figure 5d** respectively. However, we can observe the presence of not completely homogenous zones, which might be ascribed to the local variation of the absorber thickness. The upscaling process has still not been fully optimized and it will be the subject of future works. Full PL spectra and photoluminescence emission peak maps are shown in **Figure S9**. By comparing half and full stack we can observe a tenfold reduction of the I_{PLmax}, which varies from 1.6297e⁺¹⁶ to 1.2962e⁺¹⁵ ph·m⁻²·s⁻¹·sr⁻¹·nm⁻¹ (median values). The drop of PL intensity after the deposition of the hole transport layer (HTL) in steady-state PL measurements indicates the presence of non-radiative recombination at the interface between absorber and HTL^[40]. Moreover, it is worth noting that on full stacks the I_{PL-max} has maintained a good uniformity, revealing that PTAA deposition by blade coating resulted in a homogenous coverage of the perovskite thin film. Finally,

we further demonstrated the scalability of the process by replacing the dip coating with blade coating of FABr solution on 15x20cm²-sized substrate. In **Figure S10**, we resume the manufacturing process of fully blade-coated FAPbBr₃ perovskite. XRD characterization confirmed the structural properties of the FAPbBr₃ perovskite shown in **Figure 2a** for Dip-coated samples (**Figure S11**). I_{PL-max} maps of ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃ on 10x10cm²-sized substrate revealed good uniformity of the fully blade-coated FAPbBr₃ perovskite (**Figure S12**).

Figure 5. a) Semi-transparent FAPbBr₃ sample before cutting (12x10 cm²), b) a 10x10 cm² sample cut to fit the PL imaging system, c) I_{PL-max} maps of ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃, and d) ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃/PTAA architectures.

Conclusion

The present study aims to develop a scalable manufacturing process for large area semi-transparent perovskite-based devices in air environment and at low temperature ($\leq 100^{\circ}\text{C}$). The development of an up-scaling process entirely performed in air using scalable techniques at low temperature processing appears crucial going towards a future industrialization. Moreover, the semi-transparency of the device is vital to exploit perovskite technologies in BIPV field and indoor environment. In this work, we have shown how the blade-coating represents a potential candidate for replacing spin-coating as main deposition technique used for the fabrication of ST-PSC using bromide perovskite. Firstly, we demonstrated state-of-art ST-PSC entirely made by spin-coating reaching PCE and AVT values equal to 8.11 % and 47 %, respectively. Then, we developed a blade-coating process for each layer forming the device stack (SnO₂, FAPbBr₃ and PTAA). Interestingly, fully blade-coated ST-PSC show a maximum PCE of 5.8 %, AVT equal to 52 % and a bifaciality factor of 86.5 %. The optimization of the FAPbBr₃ perovskite deposition was corroborated by a thorough structural and morphology investigation based on XRD, SEM and AFM. Preliminary results on thermal stability are also encouraging for fully blade-coated devices showed negligible impact on PV performance after storage at 85°C for 1000 hours. The spatial uniformity of the blade-coated FAPbBr₃ perovskite on large 10x10cm² size substrate are evaluated by measuring PL signal using hyperspectral imaging system. This work opens the via for the future development of semi-transparent large area perovskite solar modules.

Experimental

Device Fabrication

ITO glass substrates (Kintec company, $10 \Omega/\square$ as sheet resistance) were etched by using a nanosecond UV laser in order to obtain the desired layout consisting of four small cells with an active area of 0.4 cm^2 on $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ sized substrate (**Figure S1**). For Sample B, C and D, ITO glass substrate were etched to obtain sixteen cells on $5 \times 7 \text{ cm}^2$ sized substrates. Then, the samples were rinsed in deionized water/soap solution and washed with deionized water to remove residual of soap. Afterwards, the samples were cleaned in ultrasonic bath by soaking them subsequently in deionized water and 2-propanol for 10 minutes. Prior the SnO_2 deposition, UV-ozone treatment were performed for 10 minutes. For Sample A, the SnO_2 nanoparticle ink was prepared by diluting the commercial SnO_2 dispersion (Alfa Aesar) with deionized water at 1:5 volume ratio. The diluted SnO_2 dispersion is deposited by spin coating at 2500 rpm for 40 seconds and then the samples are annealed at 100°C for 10 minutes. For Sample B, the SnO_2 nanoparticle ink was prepared by varying the dilution in deionized water. No Dilution, 1:3 v/v%, 1:5 v/v% were tested using BC technique (blade height: $70 \mu\text{m}$, $25 \mu\text{l}$ of solution, 100°C as annealing temperature, speed: 10 mm/s , No air flow). For Sample C and D, we repeated the same process using 1:3 v/v% dilution.

For Sample A and B, a stoichiometric perovskite solution (FAPbBr_3) was prepared by mixing 1.4 M PbBr_2 and 1.4 M FaBr in DMSO solvent. Then, the FAPbBr_3 perovskite film were deposited by spin coating at 4000 rpm for 20s using solvent quenching method. After 10 seconds, $200 \mu\text{l}$ of ethylacetate was dropped on the surface of the samples to induce the perovskite crystallization. The samples are then annealed at 80°C for 10 minutes. For Sample C and D, the FAPbBr_3 perovskite film were deposited by air-flow assisted blade coating using sequential deposition method (**Figure S1**). During the first step, a solution of 1.4M of PbBr_2 doped with 10 mg/ml of CsBr in DMSO was prepared. Then, the CsBr doped PbBr_2 layer was deposited by air-flow assisted blade coating at 60°C (blade height: $70 \mu\text{m}$, $25 \mu\text{l}$ of solution, 100°C as annealing temperature, speed: 5 mm/s , air flow rate: 250

L/min, air temperature: RT). The FAPbBr₃ layer is then obtained by dipping the samples in FABr solution (10mg/ml in 2-propanol) for 10 min. Alternatively, the FAPbBr₃ layer can be obtained replacing the dip coating with blade coating depositing FABr solution at 60°C with the following parameters (blade height: 70 μm, 25μl of solution, speed: 5 mm/s, No Air flow).

Doped PTAA solution (10 mg/ml, 10 KDa) in toluene was prepared by adding into the pristine solution 10 μl/ml of 4-tert-butylpyridine and 5 μl/ml of LiTFSI stock solution (170mg/ml in acetonitrile). For Sample A, B and C, the PTAA layer was obtained by spin coating at 4000rpm for 20s. For Sample D, the PTAA layer was obtained by blade coating at RT (blade height: 70 μm, 25μl of solution, speed: 100 mm/s, No Air flow). Low temperature ITO deposition was performed by magnetron sputtering at $1.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mBar and 60W RF power using an industrial in-line magnetron sputtering (KENOSISTEC S.R.L., KS 400 In-Line). Inert Ar gas is purged in the chamber (40sccm) during the ITO deposition to activate the Ar⁺ plasma. The sample holder is moved below the ITO cathode with 120 cm/min speed for 300 cycles to achieve the 100nm-thick ITO film. The sheet resistance of the sputtered ITO top contact is equal to 30 Ω/□.

Characterization

XRD

A Panalytical Empyrean X-ray diffractometer was used to perform X-ray diffraction measurements (XRD) in Bragg-Brentano configuration. Detection was accomplished by means of a PixCel 3D detector working in linear mode and a Cu-anode X-ray tube (K-Alpha1 [Å] = 1.54060; K-Alpha2 [Å] = 1.54443) was used as source. Incident optical pathway was set by divergent slits (Divergence Slit Type Fixed, Divergence Slit Size [°] = 0.2177) and patterns were collected in the 5° < 2θ < 70° angular range (Gonio acquisition, Step Size [°2θ] = 0.0260, Scan Step Time [s] = 1145, Scan Type Continuous). Samples were located onto a flat sample holder for thin films and generator parameters were kept fixed at 45mA and 40kV.

AFM

An in house developed Atomic Force Microscope (AFM) mounting a 30 μm x 30 μm scanner was used to determine morphological surface characteristics of the various samples. Non-contact mode acquisitions were collected upon several portions of each film by means of aluminum coated standard tapping AFM probes (Nanosensors), combining high operation stability with outstanding sensitivity and fast scanning ability. Images ranging from 30 x 30 to 10 x 10 μm^2 (500 points/image) were collected.

SEM

Scanning electron microscopy measurements were performed using a high-resolution SEM with FEG Schottky electron source (TESCAN MIRA).

Hyperspectral Photoluminescence Imaging

Macro view (~10 cm scale) hyperspectral photoluminescence images were acquired with Grand-EOS equipment from Photon etc.. A wide-field illuminating blue LED system (Ucube 405 nm, from UWAVE), homogeneously brightens specimens at a power of one Sun on the stage. All PL measurements were performed in an ambient atmosphere at room temperature without humidity control in the clean room. In this environment, complete reproducibility of PL acquisitions was achieved.

Photovoltaic Performance

Current density-voltage (J-V) characteristic of devices were acquired in air by using a solar simulator (ABET Sun 2000, class A) calibrated at AM 1.5 and 100 mWcm^{-2} illumination condition using a certified reference Si Cell (RERA Solutions RR-1002). The J-V characteristics were acquired in both scan directions (reverse and forward) using a scan rate of 300 mVs^{-1} and step voltage of 50 mV. A commercial setup of 4-wire source meter and several channels (Arkeo-Ariadne, Cicci Research srl) was utilized. Incident Photon-to-Current efficiency (IPCE) spectra were acquired using a commercial

setup (Arkeo-Adriadne, Cicci Research srl) based on a 300 W xenon lamp, able to acquire a spectrum from 300 to 1100 nm with a resolution of 2nm. AVT values were calculated by using the equation (1) shown in S.I..

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